

Is ICT a Boon or Curse for Human Development?

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Abstract:

Information and communication technology has influenced contemporary human life. Today even the poorest of the poor in society have smart-phones. The Covid-19 pandemic has led to an increase in the usage of ICT tools. In the educational field, we see that the teaching-learning process is dependent on ICT tools like online teaching sessions, virtual classroom, sound and music, video clips, recording of conversations between intellectuals and educationalists. The craze of video games has left the young generation awestruck. Nowadays, children learn the mechanism of ICT tools very easily due to its ease of accessibility.

The impact of ICT has both a bright and sad side, much like human life itself. It has badly affected the psyche of human beings. Children forgot the happiness of playing outdoors due to it. We are becoming too dependent on ICT even for small tasks. We are using less thinking power as calculators or computers give the solution within a fraction of seconds. The online frauds have increased these days. There is a danger of intellectual theft in the research field. Many hackers hack the sensitive information from websites and earn money. Our money transactions are sometimes unsecured and lead to economic frauds.

Living a balanced life in terms of ICT usage is the solution for these problems. We should make use of our intellectual and reasoning skills instead of ICT tools whenever possible. We should keep aside the mobiles and laptops while going to bed. We should limit the exposure of children to the screen. These are a few remedies to follow for a lifetime.

Keywords: ICT, human life, online education, screen time, covid-19, digitalization, children-parent relation, human intelligence

Introduction:

Contemporary human life is deeply affected by the internet and information and communication technology. Today the poorest of the poor of the world have mobile phones. It is the most influencing discovery and development of science. Wireless communication has connected all the distant and remote areas of the world. The information and communication tools have assisted the defence and economic systems of the world. It actually developed as a defence mechanism but slowly the private use increased. With the advent of mobiles, laptops and television; ICT entered the common life of humans. The satellites and spacecraft discoveries made it possible to connect each and every part of the world.

The information about anything in the world is available to us with one click. Millions of websites are updated every second in the world. To increase the number of visitors to the websites the web-designers take help of advertisement and offers. With this medium they earn money and continuously post the new updates. It has become a medium to connect all the interested viewers all over the world. It can be called the new culture of the internet which developed in the 20th century. Thus the information is spread through this medium and everybody comes to know within a fraction of second. But the authenticity of the information is questioned. We don't know whether the information is correct or not. There is a possibility that the information up-loader is a fraud and is trying to defame the person or company by spreading wrong information. The up-loader may use the information to increase hatred and tensions in the social life of contemporary humans. But the websites have a positive influence on contemporary human life also. There are many websites which work for human welfare and wellbeing of the world at large. Through the internet the distant viewers got connected, which was impossible otherwise.

In the covid-19 pandemic, online teaching gained importance. As social distancing and lockdown were the only remedies, the government of India encouraged online teaching for the spread of education and development of students. As a result, many teachers started teaching online with the help of information and communication tools like what's up, Zoom, Google meet, Google classroom, etc. Many students got connected through the internet and their learning did not stop at any cost. But the quality of education got hampered. The learning which was possible through face to face teaching is not happening in online teaching. The personal

involvement of the teacher in a student's education is not possible in this new teaching methodology. Many subjects like music, business management, hotel management, etc which require field work and practical knowledge cannot be taught properly through online medium. As a result, there is miscommunication between teachers and students. Students are disheartened by the situations around them and their inability to gain practical knowledge.

At the same time, the qualification and teaching skills of the teacher are questioned. Many teachers are unaware of the digital medium and are incapable of handling the problems that arise in online teaching. Many times the students solve the problems in online teaching instead of the teachers. So many institutions and colleges have given jobs to technical teams which would solve the problems and the major hurdle of teaching and learning process is removed. But still the question of the qualification and standard of the teacher is unsolved. The students must confirm the qualification and standard of the teacher before joining any online coaching or tuition and before giving money. With one click our money is lost and we don't get the standard of the teaching we are expecting by viewing the advertisement and offers. Many students can't afford android mobiles. So they are left behind in the class and the inferiority complex affects their psychology. Their interest in studies decline and they are distracted from the learning process.

The world's economic system is assisted by information and communication technology. Many databases and online sensitive information is stored and updated through ICT tools. Doing this manually is a hectic and stressful task. But because of ICT tools like the internet, computers and mobiles; this task is completed within a fraction of seconds. There are lesser chances of errors in this task. Many complicated calculations are done by computer accurately. Once the programming and commands are given to the computer, it applies it to many files and transactions within a second. The digitalization of money demanded online transfer and exchange of money. For these transactions ICT tools like bank's websites, bank's applications, android mobiles, applications like Phone-pe, Google pay, ATM played an important role.

These services are useful, but so are the frauds committed using these tools. We need to be aware of the monetary frauds happening around us daily. Today banks also make the customer aware of these frauds in the form of instructions and advertisements. We should never share the pin code of online transactions with anybody. The four digits of the ATM card should not be shared. We need to keep an

eye on the messages of login and transaction details given by the bank. If the transaction is not done by us, we should immediately contact the bank either online through email or personally by visiting the nearby branch of the bank. The hacker hacked the bank website and crimes happened. So the security check and updating the website or bank's application is a must. By updating it from time to time, the viruses used by these hackers can be detected and destroyed before causing any harm to our economic property or our mobile and laptops.

As there is economic property, similarly there is intellectual property. Our intellectual property is the research work, our findings and our contribution to the field we belong. When we upload these works online, there is a possibility of intellectual theft. Our intellectual property is stolen by the hackers and frauds and used for their profit. They claim our findings and research work as theirs without taking our permission or acknowledging our contribution in bibliography or references which they provide. This is intellectual theft and today we can take help of law and avoid such crimes to happen. The copyright rights are owned by the author only. If any such fraud happens, he or she can take help of law and the fraud can be sentenced to jail or other punishments. Our identity in online media can be used for spreading rumours and false information using ICT tools. But we can go against them in court and such frauds can be stopped.

Today children are exposed to the internet at a very small age. They have their own android phones and laptops. Because of which they explore information and communication technology at an early age. But they are unaware of the outside world. The constant use of ICT tools has a bad impact on their mental health and psychology. In the age of playing outdoors and exercising outside, these children became slaves of machines. The video games and virtual playstations have impacted their childhood badly. The television brought a different ideology in their life. They know more than their parents; but they are also exposed to knowledge which is harmful for their age.

Their parents need to keep a check on what their children are watching on television. They should set a time limit on their watching. There are many films and TV serials which are not made for children below eighteen years of age. But there are positive outputs of children using the ICT tools as well. They want to be heroes and find solutions in problematic situations because of the use of adventurous video games and good TV serials. They get training on how to behave in such conditions in life. Science can be easily taught through educational programs. With entertainment,

education can be taught easily and happily. In covid-19 pandemic, online education is the best option for children to learn. We should keep aside the mobiles and laptops while going to bed. We should limit the exposure of children to the screen.

Conclusion:

The use of information and communication technology is the need of the hour. Online education and equally accessibility are boons of these ICT tools. But, there are more and more internet scammers. The scientific community is vulnerable to intellectual theft. Many hackers steal confidential data from websites in order to profit. Sometimes our financial transactions are unsafe and result in frauds against the financial system. Through all the evaluation, we can say that information and communication technology has both positive and negative impact on human life. The positive impact can be increased, if we take measures and remedies to avoid the negative impact. Living a balanced life in terms of ICT usage is the solution for these problems. We should make use of our intellectual and reasoning skills instead of ICT tools whenever possible. We are responsible for the mental and physical health of ourselves and our family. So it is our responsibility to make less use of ICT tools but at the same time to make use of them when there is necessity and urgency.

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